

Research Data and FAIR signposting report: best practice and guidance document

Janete Saldanha Bach, Yudong Zhang, Brigitte Mathiak, and Peter Mutschke.

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Abstract (in German)

Die FAIR-Grundsätze sind offen für Interpretationen, was zu unterschiedlichen Bewertungen der Einhaltung der Grundsätze durch verschiedene Instrumente wie F-UJI führt, die leicht unterschiedliche Ansätze anwenden. FAIR Signposting spielt eine entscheidende Rolle bei der Standardisierung dieser Bewertungen, indem es Inkonsistenzen beseitigt und eine einheitlichere Auslegung der FAIR-Grundsätze über verschiedene Bewertungsplattformen hinweg gewährleistet. Das FAIR Signposting Projekt von KonsortSWD zielt darauf ab, den FAIR Signposting Standard [1] von Forschungsdatenzentren, die mit KonsortSWD assoziiert sind, zu implementieren, um deren FAIRness Scores durch Standardisierung von URIs zu verbessern. Dieser Ansatz ist ein zentraler Benchmark von FAIRen Metadaten und soll die Auffindbarkeit und allgemeine FAIRness von Forschungsdatensätzen verbessern. Das Projekt verfolgt zwei Ziele: Das erste umfasst die operative Umsetzung eines Prototyps bei GESIS und seine anschließende Verbreitung bei Use Case Partnern. Das zweite Ziel ist die Erstellung eines Dokuments mit Best Practices und Leitlinien sowie eines umfassenden Berichts, in dem die Erfahrungen des Projekts, die grundlegenden Konzepte und die vorbereitenden technischen Arbeiten beschrieben werden. Das Projekt stellt eine gemeinsame Anstrengung zur Standardisierung der FAIR-Metadatenbewertung dar, die die Datenzugänglichkeit von Forschungsdatenzentren erheblich verbessert.

Abstract

The FAIR principles are inherently open to interpretation, leading to varying compliance assessments across different tools, such as F-UJI, FAIR-Checker, or FAIR Evaluator. These tools apply slightly different approaches, leading to different assessment scores. FAIR Signposting is critical in standardizing these evaluations by addressing inconsistencies and ensuring a uniform interpretation of FAIR principles across various assessment platforms. The FAIR Signposting project for KonsortSWD aims to adopt and implement the FAIR Signposting standard [1] of research data centers associated with KonsortSWD, improving their FAIRness scores by standardizing URIs. This approach is a key benchmark in evaluating FAIR metadata and is designed to enhance research datasets' findability and overall FAIRness. The project has two main tasks: the first involves the operational implementation of a prototype at GESIS and its subsequent deployment among use case partners, aiming to broaden participation and application. In all cases, linked metadata of research objects received a higher FAIRness score through FAIR Signposting, where 75% of use cases doubled their scores. The second task focuses on creating a best practice and guidance document alongside a comprehensive report detailing the project's experiences, foundational concepts, and preparatory technical work. The project represents a collaborative effort to standardize FAIR metadata assessment, significantly improving the data accessibility of research data centers.

Keywords: FAIR data. FAIR Metrics. Data FAIRness. FAIR Signposting. Research Data findability. FAIR Principles. Metadata. Metadata standards. FAIR Automated assessment.

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Authors	Janete S. Bach - https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9011-5837 Brigitte Mathiak - https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1793-9615 Yudong Zhang - https://orcid.org/0009-0006-7108-475X Peter Mutschke - https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3517-8071
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KonsortSWD Measure 5.2: Enhancing data findability

Research Data and FAIR signposting report: best practice and guidance document

1 Introduction

The FAIR Signposting project of KonsortSWD relies on implementing the FAIR Signposting [1] recommended patterns. KonsortSWDⁱ is a consortium of the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI)ⁱⁱ, explicitly addressing the needs of the social, behavioral, educational, and economic sciences. NFDI focuses on advancing science and research by establishing a comprehensive, national-level research data infrastructure. This involves developing interoperable and sustainable solutions for managing research data and coordinating the creation of a networked information infrastructure. By ensuring the efficient use of data across Germany's scientific ecosystem, the NFDI addresses both cross-disciplinary and interdisciplinary research needs, fostering collaboration and innovation. KonsortSWD aims to strengthen the research data infrastructure for the social, behavioral, educational, and economic sciences. KonsortSWD provides tailored services to researchers and research data centers, emphasizing data-sharing practices that align with the FAIR principles. It seeks to enhance data availability and provide comprehensive support throughout the research lifecycle, particularly in managing sensitive data effectively.

KonsortSWD is organized into task areas (TA) and Measures (M); this report is an outcome of Measure TA.5-M.2 (short 5.2: Enhancing Data Findability). The primary objective of Measure 5.2 is to improve the findability of KonsortSWD metadata and non-sensitive research data on the web. The measure ensures that KonsortSWD data is better visible to users through general search engines and data portals by adopting common web standards and search engine optimization (SEO) practices. The initiative also emphasizes refining existing metadata schemas and contributing to developing an NFDI-wide metadata standard for web visibility. Additionally, it supports the integration of Research Data Centers (RDCs) into a federated infrastructure by contributing to high-quality and uniform metadata standards. Through these efforts, KonsortSWD seeks to enhance discoverability and, by this, reuse research data.

To advance this further, Measure 5.2 of KonsortSWD initiated a focused initiative in collaboration with partners (see Section 5) to introduce FAIR Signposting into KonsortSWD. The FAIR Signposting framework is highly relevant to TA.5-M.2 as it provides standardized mechanisms for linking and discovering digital resources, which aligns with the measure's goal of enhancing data findability by ensuring that KonsortSWD metadata and research data are consistently discoverable and reusable across diverse platforms and search environments.

FAIR Signposting establishes a new connection with existing standards, i.e., the IANA Linksⁱⁱⁱ relation types (detailed in section 3.1), with target metadata of scholarly objects guided by the FAIR principles. FAIR Signposting pattern [2] was developed by the FAIR Metrics subgroup from the EOSC Task Force on FAIR Metrics and Data Quality [1] in collaboration with other

ⁱ <https://www.konsortswd.de/ueber-uns/konsortswd/>

ⁱⁱ <https://www.nfdi.de>

ⁱⁱⁱ <https://www.iana.org/assignments/link-relations/link-relations.xhtml>

community stakeholders^{iv} during a series of hackathon events. This pattern became the new de facto standard for assessing metadata FAIRness. Therefore, the FAIR Signposting project for KonsortSWD adopts it to improve data findability within KonsortSWD data centers, and the main deliverables are explained below:

Deliverable one focuses on implementing FAIR Signposting at GESIS and with use case partners. This involves putting FAIR Signposting into productive operation at GESIS, followed by implementation with partners like LfBi, DIPF, DZHW, and DIW SOEP. The task aims to enhance collaboration among KonsortSWD data centers.

Deliverable two is dedicated to developing a best practice and guidance document alongside a comprehensive report detailing experiences, conceptual foundations, and technical preparatory work. This task documents the practical guidance implementation of FAIR Signposting and provides valuable insights and directions for future deployments, detailed in the present document.

This document serves as the final report for the FAIR Signposting project for KonsortSWD. It outlines the efforts and strategic implementations undertaken in 2024 to improve the FAIRness of metadata within KonsortSWD's data centers.

^{iv} including representatives from several of the publicly available FAIR assessment tools (The FAIR Evaluator, F-UJI, FAIR Enough/SATIFYD4 (manual), FAIR Enough (automated), FAIR Checker, ENVRI-FAIR, and FAIRshake [8]) and coders and designers from a variety of FAIR-oriented data infrastructure and standards projects such as RO-Crate [9], and FAIRsharing9, matured under and endorsed by the RDA

1.1 Motivation

KonsortSWD Measure 5.2 has been endorsing efforts regarding Findability, particularly for datasets, in Research Data Centers (RDCs) of KonsortSWD for the last three years. A summary of results from these efforts varies regarding a range of outcomes, here organized by topics across multiple outcomes.

The initial reports for KonsortSWD Measure 5.2 (Milestones 1, 2, and 3) [3] focused on establishing a baseline understanding of data findability practices within the Research Data Centers (RDCs) network. Surveys and interviews revealed significant variability in metadata standards, technical tools, and SEO adoption across RDCs. Common challenges included inconsistent metadata quality, lack of resources, and insufficient adoption of tools like schema.org and sitemaps. Recommendations emphasized the need for structured metadata, integration of SEO practices, and enhanced use of metadata standards like Dublin Core and schema.org. A strategy was developed to improve data discoverability by proposing the adoption of schema.org, creating dedicated landing pages, and continuously monitoring web visibility metrics. These reports laid the foundation for later evaluations by offering practical recommendations tailored to the specific needs of RDCs.

The reports also detailed SEO monitoring tools like SISTRIX to analyse RDCs' online visibility. Findings highlighted disparities in keyword rankings, visibility indices, and URL optimization. The recommendations included adopting standardized metadata practices and encouraging collaborations to improve data discoverability. Community engagement activities and workshops facilitated knowledge sharing and feedback, enabling RDCs to refine their strategies and address key barriers to findability.

The subsequent report (Milestones 4 and 5) [4], evaluated the implementation and impact of previously recommended strategies while introducing new activities, such as FAIRness assessments. The analysis revealed gradual improvements in SEO adoption and web visibility among RDCs, with increased usage of tools like Matomo and Google Search Console. The application of schema.org metadata and optimization of landing pages improved searchability, though challenges such as limited resources and varying technical expertise persisted. However, follow-up surveys revealed progress in adopting SEO tools (29% to 53%) and increasing dedicated RDC websites (88% to 94%). Testimonials from RDCs like DZHW and DIPF highlighted improvements in data findability through applied recommendations. The FAIR assessments highlighted gaps in metadata quality, licensing policies, and the adoption of standardized web protocols. To address these issues, targeted recommendations included embedding metadata in web pages, adopting signposting links, and optimizing keywords for better findability.

The Measure's community engagement was a central focus of this report, emphasizing collaboration with stakeholders through workshops, consultations, and participation in NFDI working groups. The "Data Findability in a Changing Ecosystem" workshop fostered discussions on challenges like cross-domain data discovery, citation practices, and knowledge graph implementation. Feedback from these engagements underscored the importance of interoperable systems and tailored solutions for diverse user needs. While the reports acknowledged the progress, they emphasized the dynamic nature of data findability and the need for ongoing efforts, including further collaborations and developing FAIR-compliant frameworks to support RDCs in the long term. The summary of the main results is listed below:

FAIRness assessment and compliance were applied at GESIS, where we conducted an automatic FAIR assessment using the F-UJI tool [5], which employs the FAIRsFAIR metrics [6] in a machine-readable fashion. We assessed the F-UJI tool against GESIS Search^v in the context of KonsortSWD, motivated by the European landscape study [7], which led us to improve our metadata. GESIS Search is a research data discovery platform provided by GESIS – Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences, which supports social science researchers by offering access to high-quality data, tools, and services. It is designed to facilitate the search and retrieval of research data, metadata, and associated resources in compliance with the FAIR principles. The assessment of GESIS data repositories using the F-UJI tool identified systematic weaknesses in metadata quality, including missing keywords, incomplete licensing information, and lack of machine-readable provenance data [8]. While the metadata met basic findability requirements for aggregators like Google Dataset Search, significant improvements were recommended to enhance machine-actionable FAIR compliance, such as adopting structured metadata elements like schema.org and standardized protocols. The F-UJI tool revealed gaps such as the absence of the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH), insufficient use of recognized semantic vocabularies, and failure to specify file formats like .csv. These issues led to deductions in FAIRness scores, particularly under Accessibility and Reusability principles. The Measure provided an action plan for improvements and recommendations, including embedding metadata directly in HTML/XHTML, enhancing metadata descriptions with controlled vocabularies, and using standardized licenses from SPDX. The action plan also emphasized improving interoperability by aligning metadata schemas with community standards and adopting FAIR-aligned tools for automated metadata harvesting. Modifications to metadata structures and protocols, such as adding JSON-LD elements to landing pages, resulted in improved scores during subsequent evaluations, starting with 43% and reaching a score of 79% after improvements. The main contribution is the recommendations that serve as a roadmap for GESIS and other institutions to improve metadata quality and alignment with the FAIR principles. We have also conducted other studies and tests on automatic [8], [9], [10], [11] and manual [12], [13] assessments of our resources. KonsortSWD Measure 5.2 has also supported the community in improving FAIRness for research data [14], [15].

Our vision for FAIRness assessment has been advocating for a “FAIR by Design” approach, a similar practice well known in the privacy domain, so-called Privacy by Design (PbD) [16] [17]), where protection measures are embedded directly into technology from their inception. In the context of FAIR, “FAIR by Design” aims to align research data infrastructures with FAIR principles through their entire lifecycle [9]. In this sense, we adopted FAIR Signposting. This pattern enhances the FAIRness of digital resources by embedding machine-readable typed links, such as those pointing to metadata, persistent identifiers (PIDs), and licenses, directly within web resources. FAIR Signposting aligns with our “FAIR by design” vision, i.e., the FAIR principles should be ensured early in product or service development and embedded in the research data infrastructures from the beginning. In this sense, FAIR Signposting aligns completely since standardized URIs are a way to guide machines in navigating the research scholarly objects and reading metadata accordingly, reducing inconsistencies and, therefore, increasing FAIR Scores. Our motivation for proposing and executing the FAIR Signposting Project for KonsortSWD is to present a framework to enhance the FAIRness of metadata at KonsortSWD-associated data centers within the NFDI, mainly to improve dataset findability by:

^v See <https://search.gesis.org/>

- **Objective:** Improve the findability and usability of research data by implementing FAIR Signposting, a standardized approach that helps address metadata inconsistencies
- **Approach:** Use of tools like F-UJI to assess and improve FAIR compliance by linking metadata with persistent identifiers (PIDs) and standardized URIs
- **Final Product:** A set of best practices and guidelines for FAIR Signposting implementation
- **Target Group:** Research Data Centers (RDCs) associated with KonsortSWD and their researchers
- **Benefits for NFDI:** Enhanced metadata findability and interoperability, leading to increased FAIRness scores

Adopting the signposting approach to improve FAIRness reflects the integration of automated tools and standardized metadata formats, which are essential for modern infrastructure [18] to address the problem of dataset findability. This report is structured as follows:

Section 2. FAIR Principles and Signposting explains the FAIR principles and introduces FAIR Signposting as a framework to embed machine-readable links (e.g., cite-as, describedby) in metadata, addressing inconsistencies in FAIR assessments and improving data interoperability and discovery.

Section 3 covers the FAIR Signposting Specifications. The technical implementation of FAIR Signposting involves embedding relation types like cite-as and license through HTTP headers or standalone linksets. These methods ensure consistent metadata exposure and interoperability across platforms.

Section 4, Assessment Methods and Tools, describes automated tools like F-UJI and FAIR-Checker [42] alongside manual assessments to evaluate FAIR compliance based on the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model. These methods ensure systematic measurement of metadata quality and findability.

In section 5. Implementation Stories are presented in case studies from GESIS and other institutions that demonstrate how FAIR Signposting was implemented, overcoming challenges like resource constraints and metadata inconsistencies, and improving FAIRness scores and data visibility.

Section 6. Best Practices and Validation provides practical guidelines for implementing FAIR Signposting, including adopting schema.org standards and creating linksets. Validation tools help ensure compliance and maintain improved metadata practices.

The report concludes with section 7. Conclusions and Recommendations highlight measurable improvements in data findability and FAIRness, recommending broader adoption of FAIR Signposting, refinement of metadata standards, and ongoing community collaboration to address evolving challenges. In Section 8. Appendices and References present the supplementary materials, including detailed examples of metadata structures, relation links, and tools, providing technical guidance and citations for stakeholders implementing FAIR Signposting.

1.2 The problems affecting the findability of datasets

Challenges in dataset retrieval arise primarily due to insufficient metadata, domain variability, and diverse user needs [19]. A greater emphasis on metadata richness, consistent use of persistent identifiers, and catalog usability is needed to enhance searchability [20]. Poor or missing metadata directly impacts the discoverability and usability of datasets [21].

Inconsistent metadata formats and missing descriptive elements, such as keywords, descriptions, or licensing, hinder data discovery and reuse [19], [22]. Efforts to standardize metadata formats (e.g., DataCite, Dublin Core, and DCAT) and ensure machine-readability are critical [23]. Metadata should include detailed descriptions, provenance, and structured relationships between datasets to improve findability and accessibility [24], [25]. However, issues like unclear licensing, incomplete descriptions, and fragmented and poorly indexed metadata at repositories restrict data discovery [18]. Dataset metadata (e.g., time frame, sampling size, related documentation) is critical for assessing relevance and quality [19].

Additionally, the lack of persistent identifiers (PIDs) (e.g., DOIs, Handles standard) significantly affects the stability of datasets. Without a PID, datasets might not have a stable, unique, and resolvable link for citation or discovery. Datasets requiring set baseline standards for FAIR compliance address specific requirements, such as a dataset must have a PID, include metadata in standard formats, and be listed in at least one central data catalog [19].

Beyond metadata quality and PIDs, community norms and trust significantly influence search behavior [23]. Data search is a complex socio-technical process requiring technological solutions and social support systems [23]. The social, contextual, and technological factors in data discovery highlight the interactions between individuals with contextual and community factors. As a socio-technical process, data search promotes an interplay between social behaviors and technical tools when locating research data [23]. Although most studies in data search research focus on tool development rather than user practices [23], data search involves both technical tools (e.g., APIs, repositories) and social interactions (e.g., collaboration, author contact, data exchange practices) [23]. Social networks and collaborations are critical for discovering and accessing data, since researchers often rely on personal networks or mentorship for dataset discovery when digital tools fall short [25], with knowledge usually passed from senior to junior researchers or shared among peers [18].

Addressing these challenges requires collaborative approaches among researchers, infrastructure providers, community project recommendations, and policymakers. For example, the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) proposes a multi-layered approach involving policies, practices, and infrastructure to embed FAIR principles into the research lifecycle [26]. In this sense, FAIR Signposting also reflects a solution that aligns with the broader EOSC objectives. The reason is that it addresses standardized metrics and tools to assess the FAIRness of digital resources while ensuring that this outcome is a multi-stakeholder, community-agreed solution, and this collaboration reflects the social interaction aspect. In this sense, metadata standardization, persistent identifier implementation, and interoperable tools must be associated with access and long-term preservation policies designed by institutions and decision-makers to ensure sustainable and efficient dataset retrieval.

2 FAIR principles and FAIR Signposting

Since its publication, the FAIR Data Principles [27] have become the cornerstone of research data management. However, they are subjective and can be interpreted differently. The FAIR Principles are widely applied to research data infrastructures. However, assessing how much a data infrastructure implements these principles into tangible practices is still tricky. FAIR assessment tools like F-UJI^{vi} and others have been developed to measure these principles automatically. However, each tool measures the FAIRness of a digital object slightly differently. Consequently, it leads to different scores, and many issues related to FAIR compliance are identified based on the ambiguous interpretation of metadata provision [1]. It is a huge challenge to transform the FAIR principles into concrete practice, and FAIR signposting aims to fulfill this accomplishment. Hence, FAIR signposting has an essential role in standardizing the measurement process. It aims for simplicity to achieve meaningful interoperability for machines to navigate scholarly objects. It uses a limited set of relations to guide automated agents unambiguously from identifiers to metadata to data and vice versa.

FAIR signposting explores the notion that landing pages are readable by humans but not optimized for machines. The primary goals outlined in the FAIR Signposting standard include harmonizing the metadata harvesting workflows of various FAIR assessment tools and creating benchmark reference environments [1]. This harmonization aims to ensure consistency in FAIR evaluations to assist data repositories in achieving (fair) FAIRness scores for research data across many tools. It also addresses the importance of adopting metadata standards and values the role of key stakeholders, such as builders of assessment tools, data publishers, and organizations like the EOSC. It suggests that efforts to make FAIR assessment more consistent will support transparency and fairness in evaluating digital objects' FAIRness.

The FAIR signposting standardization is possible due to the established connection between selected relation links, previously defined in the IANA registry^{vii} (detailed in section 3.1), as depicted in Figure 1.

^{vi} <https://www.fairsfair.eu/f-uji-automated-fair-data-assessment-tool>

^{vii} <https://www.iana.org/assignments/link-relations/link-relations.xhtml>

Figure 1: Relation of selected relation links from the IANA registry

FAIR Signposting selected relations links (detailed in section 3.1) combined can build a path to make the scholarly web easy to navigate by machines; for example, each relation link indicates to the machines what to follow, as signed with the Signposting relation links to find Author, PIDs, or other content discoverability, and so on. Table 1 demonstrates how each one of the FAIR signposting relations links ensures **FAIRness** by:

FAIR principle	How FAIR signposting ensures FAIRness	Relation link in FAIR signposting
F	Persistent Identifiers (PIDs): The <code>cite-as</code> link ensures the object has a globally unique and resolvable reference	<code>rel="cite-as"</code>
	Metadata discovery: The <code>describedby</code> link allows machines to locate metadata that describes the object	<code>rel="describedby"</code>
A	Providing links in standard HTTP headers, HTML, and <code>linkset</code> documents that can be accessed using web protocols	<code>rel="linkset"</code>
	Link datasets with related publications and other data repositories	<code>rel="collection"</code>
I	Using standardized link relation types defined in the web standards (IANA registry)	<code>rel="describedby"</code>
	Linking to metadata and resources in machine-readable formats (e.g., JSON, RDF) with explicit media types	<code>rel="type", rel="item"</code>
R	Providing rich metadata (<code>describedby</code>) that includes provenance, licensing (<code>license</code>), and context for the object, enabling reuse in diverse workflows	<code>rel="license"</code>
	Linking to detailed descriptions and related resources to enable reuse	<code>rel="collection"</code>

Table 1 : Mapping between FAIR Principles and FAIR Signposting

3 FAIR Signposting Specification

The foundational aspects of FAIR data publishing are its association with a PID and its explicit association with its metadata. A PID ensures that every dataset or digital object, such as a DOI, can be uniquely and persistently identified and enables citation, retrieval, and linking within digital ecosystems. The explicit association between data and metadata provides descriptive information about the data, such as its purpose, structure, provenance, and how it can be accessed. It ensures that machines and humans can efficiently interpret, locate, and use the data. Therefore, FAIR Signposting bridges the gap between human and machine accessibility by defining and standardizing *URLs*. The essence of FAIR Signposting lies in using typed (*relation*) links, which are structured hyperlinks embedded in the HTTP headers or HTML *<head>* section of landing pages and content resources. These relation links serve as "signposts," guiding machines to essential metadata, persistent identifiers, and related resources. Through the adoption of *relation types* and integration with metadata standards, FAIR Signposting supports a scalable and interoperable framework for managing scholarly resources.

Hence, the key components of FAIR Signposting are uniform link types (e.g., *cite-as*, describedby, item, see Table 3) that are registered in the IANA Link Relations registry^{viii}, using selected links to directly connect them with Persistent Identifiers (PIDs), Metadata, Content Resources, and their associated files. It ensures interoperability, consistency, and compatibility across FAIR assessment tools. FAIR Signposting has two Implementation levels: Level 1, which embeds essential relation links in HTTP headers or HTML *<head>* for quick and minimal metadata exposure, and Level 2, which uses standalone linkset documents for comprehensive metadata and resource connections, avoiding header size limitations (See 3.2).

3.1 Core Principles of FAIR Signposting: *relation links*

The FAIR Signposting Profile provides various *relation types* such as "author," "cite-as," and "describedby," among others (see Table 3), essential for linking and describing scholarly web resources using FAIR principles. FAIR Signposting employs these standardized Link Headers to:

- a) Connect datasets to their unique identifiers and associated metadata records
- b) Allow machines to navigate the metadata ecosystem unambiguously
- c) Enable automation to find and retrieve data and its descriptions

Relation links are structured hyperlinks with a specific **link relation type**^{ix} to describe the relationship between resources on the web. These relation links are machine-readable and enable automated systems to understand the connections between these resources. The FAIR Signposting standard reused the IANA Link Relations registry^x, previously defined relation links. Then it included HTTP headers, as HTML *<link>* elements, or as a Link Set to connect with a document. These specific approaches are defined at FAIR Signposting Profile convey relation links at HTTP response headers for dynamic and programmatic access, HTML *<link>* elements are embedded within the head section of an HTML document for human and machine

^{viii} <https://www.iana.org/assignments/link-relations/link-relations.xhtml>

^{ix} <https://signposting.org/FAIR/>

^x <https://www.iana.org/assignments/link-relations/link-relations.xhtml>

discoverability, and Link Set uses a standalone document that is made discoverable through a typed link with the linkset relation type.

Table 3 shows the Relation Types that are used for the FAIR Signposting Profile. These types are used to meaningfully interlink resources representing a scholarly web artifact. The meaning of each type is based on a more formal language used in the specification that defines it. The descriptions provide their specific use for the FAIR Signposting Profile.

Examples of Relation Links:

- `cite-as`: Links to a scholarly object's persistent identifier (e.g., DOI)
- `describedby`: Points to metadata that describes the object
- `item`: Links to content resources associated with the object (e.g., data files)

Table 2 provides all the Signposting relation links, which are sourced from the IANA Link Relation Registry, with their definitions and purposes rooted in specific Requests for Comments (RFCs) or registration entries^{xi}:

Relation Links	Source	First Defined	Specification
<code>author</code>	IANA	HTML 4.0 Specification (1997), RFC 5988	HTML 4.0, RFC 5988
<code>cite-as</code>	IANA	2017	<code>cite-as</code> in IANA
<code>describedby</code>	IANA	RFC 5988 (<i>Web Linking</i> , 2010)	RFC 5988
<code>describes</code>	IANA	2016	<code>describes</code> in IANA
<code>type</code>	IANA	RFC 5988 (<i>Web Linking</i> , 2010)	RFC 5988
<code>license</code>	IANA	RFC 4946 (<i>The Atom Publishing Protocol</i> , 2007)	RFC 4946
<code>item</code>	IANA	RFC 6573 (<i>The Item and Collection Link Relations</i> , 2012)	RFC 6573
<code>collection</code>	IANA	RFC 6573 (<i>The Item and Collection Link Relations</i> , 2012)	RFC 6573

Table 2: Signposting relation Links sourced from the IANA Link Relation Registry

Table 3 lists the core relation links in FAIR Signposting with examples, descriptions, and content.

^{xi} RFCs are formal documents published by the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF).

Relation Type	FAIR Signposting specification	Description	Examples	Content
<i>author</i>	<i>rel="author"</i>	The link's target is a URI for the author of the resource, which is the origin of the link.	Links to the scholarly object's author (s) often point to Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for humans, such as ORCID or similar.	https://doi.org/10.4232/1.13564 → <i>rel="author"</i> → https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1825-0097
<i>cite-as</i>	<i>rel="cite-as"</i>	The link's target is a persistent URI for the resource that is the origin of the link.	Persistent Identifiers (PIDs): Globally unique and resolvable identifiers for the object (e.g., DOI, Handle, ARK)	https://doi.org/10.4232/1.13564 → <i>rel="cite-as"</i> → https://doi.org/10.4232/1.13564
<i>describedby</i>	<i>rel="describedby"</i>	The link's target provides metadata describing the resource that is the origin of the link.	Links to URIs where metadata describing the object is available and where there is descriptive information about the object, such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ·Title ·Authors and affiliations (linked via ORCID or ROR) ·Abstract or description ·Keywords ·Temporal and geospatial information ·Related works (e.g., datasets or articles) 	https://doi.org/10.4232/1.13564 → <i>rel="describedby"</i> → https://example.com/metadata/dataset_metadata.xml

<i>describes</i>	<i>rel="describes"</i>	The origin of the link is a resource that provides metadata that describes the resource that is the link's target. It is the inverse of the <i>describedby</i> relation type.	Points to a description of another object and specifies the type of the scholarly object (e.g., dataset, article, software) using controlled vocabularies like Schema.org.	
<i>type</i>	<i>rel="type"</i>	The link's target is the URI for a class of resources to which the resource that is the origin of the link belongs.	Specifies the type of the object using controlled vocabularies, such as schema.org.	https://doi.org/10.4232/1.13564 → <i>rel="type"</i> → https://schema.org/Dataset
<i>license</i>	<i>rel="license"</i>	The link's target is the URI of a license that applies to the resource that is the origin of the link.	Links to machine-readable licenses (e.g., Creative Commons, SPDX URIs, or similar standards)	https://doi.org/10.4232/1.13564 → <i>rel="license"</i> → https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-4.0.html
<i>item</i>	<i>rel="item"</i>	The origin of the link is a collection of resources, and the link's target is a resource that belongs to that collection. It is the inverse of the <i>collection</i> relation type.	Points to URIs where the object's content is available (e.g., downloadable files). Or direct links to the files associated with the object (e.g., datasets, PDFs, or software).	https://doi.org/10.4232/1.13564 → <i>rel="item"</i> → https://example.com/dataset_content.csv

collection	rel="collection"	The origin of the link is a resource that belongs to a collection, and the target of the link is the collection to which it belongs. It is the inverse of the item relation type.	Links to related objects and points to a collection the object belongs to (e.g., collections, citations, derived datasets).
------------	------------------	---	---

Table 3: FAIR Signposting relation links^{xii}.

^{xii} Adapted from <https://signposting.org/FAIR/> and enriched with more examples

Relation Links enable straightforward navigation for machines, as they can "follow" links to specific resources (e.g., metadata, content files). It also facilitates scalability since it handles large datasets without transferring full content initially. It is suitable for cross-domain usability as it works for all resource types (e.g., datasets, articles) and across diverse platforms.

Each link relation type (e.g., author, cite-as, license, etc.) can be used multiple times on the same landing page to point to multiple resources. This allows for flexibility in representing complex scholarly objects that may have:

- a) Multiple **authors** (e.g., pointing to multiple ORCID profiles)
- b) Multiple **identifiers** (e.g., DOI, Handle, or ARK)
- c) Multiple **licenses** (e.g., different licenses for different parts of the object)
- d) Multiple **types** (e.g., an object classified as a dataset and a software)
- e) Multiple **content resources** (e.g., different file formats or versions of content)
- f) Multiple **metadata resources** (e.g., metadata in different schemas or formats)

Figure 2 depicts an example of DOI 10.1594/PANGAEA.86790, a dataset with many repeatable link relation types. For instance, rel="author" is repeated five times, while rel="describedby" is repeated eight times.

FDS_SIGNPOSTING_CHECK on FDOs :

<https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.867908>

```
{
  "responseCode": 1,
  "type": "Signposting Check",
  "content": [
    {
      "signpostingCheck": {
        "PID": "https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.867908",
        "signpostingHtmlLinks": {
          "1": "cite-as: \u003chttps://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.867908\u003e"
          "2": "author: \u003chttps://orcid.org/0000-0002-7527-5880\u003e"
          "3": "author: \u003chttps://orcid.org/0000-0001-8877-1325\u003e"
          "4": "author: \u003chttps://orcid.org/0000-0003-1291-8524\u003e"
          "5": "author: \u003chttps://orcid.org/0000-0002-0856-5183\u003e"
          "6": "author: \u003chttps://orcid.org/0000-0003-2612-8347\u003e"
          "7": "describedby: \u003chttps://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.867908\u003e"
          "8": "describedby: \u003chttps://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.867908\u003e"
          "9": "describedby: \u003chttps://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.867908\u003e"
          "10": "describedby: \u003chttps://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.867908\u003e"
          "11": "describedby: \u003chttps://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.867908\u003e"
          "12": "describedby: \u003chttps://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.867908\u003e"
          "13": "describedby: \u003chttps://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.867908\u003e"
          "14": "describedby: \u003chttps://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.867908\u003e"
          "15": "item: \u003chttps://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.867908\u003e"
        },
        "signpostingHttpLinks": {
          "1": "cite-as: \u003chttps://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.867908\u003e"
          "2": "author: \u003chttps://orcid.org/0000-0002-7527-5880\u003e"
          "3": "author: \u003chttps://orcid.org/0000-0001-8877-1325\u003e"
          "4": "author: \u003chttps://orcid.org/0000-0003-1291-8524\u003e"
          "5": "author: \u003chttps://orcid.org/0000-0002-0856-5183\u003e"
          "6": "author: \u003chttps://orcid.org/0000-0003-2612-8347\u003e"
          "7": "describedby: \u003chttps://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.867908\u003e"
          "8": "describedby: \u003chttps://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.867908\u003e"
          "9": "describedby: \u003chttps://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.867908\u003e"
          "10": "describedby: \u003chttps://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.867908\u003e"
          "11": "describedby: \u003chttps://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.867908\u003e"
          "12": "describedby: \u003chttps://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.867908\u003e"
          "13": "describedby: \u003chttps://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.867908\u003e"
          "14": "describedby: \u003chttps://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.867908\u003e"
          "15": "item: \u003chttps://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.867908\u003e"
        }
      }
    }
  ]
}
```

Figure 2: Repeated FAIR Signposting relation links from DOI 10.1594/PANGAEA.86790

Repeating FAIR Signposts elements in representing complex scholarly objects may also lead to higher FAIRness scores, as demonstrated in Figure 2. Figure 3 below shows the FAIRness score of 87% of a DOI 10.1594/PANGAEA.86790 assessed against F-UJI, the same DOI used previously as an example in Figure 2.

Figure 3: FAIRness score of DOI: <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.867908>^{xiii}.

3.2 Signposting levels

Signposting levels 1 and 2 provide different mechanisms for conveying relation links and vary in the extent of the relation links and `linksets` they offer. These levels cater to different implementation needs, providing flexibility for resource metadata and accessibility. Level 1 is more straightforward, focusing on delivering essential links directly via HTTP headers. Level 2 introduces a more detailed approach, encapsulating extended metadata and resource relationships within a dedicated `linkset` document, increasing precision and granularity.

Signposting Level 1 focuses on providing essential relation links directly in HTTP headers, ensuring that critical metadata and identifiers are accessible during resource retrieval. Mandatory Fields:

- a) `cite-as`: Points to the persistent identifier (e.g., DOI) for the object
- b) `describedby`: Provides links to metadata describing the object
- c) `type`: Specifies the type of the object, often using vocabularies like Schema.org (e.g., dataset, article)
- d) Optional Fields:
 - o Links to content resources (`item`), such as downloadable files or data
 - o Links to author information, typically through persistent identifiers like ORCID

Signposting Level 2 expands the offering of a set of links, extending Level 1 by offering comprehensive relation links in a standalone `linkset` document, allowing greater scalability and detailed resource interconnections. A `linkset` is an external file consolidating all the links associated with a scholarly object. These documents use the RFC 9264 `linkset` format^{xiv}. This approach enables machine agents to efficiently navigate all relevant resources, supporting a complete and structured view of the scholarly object. At FAIR Signposting, mandatory Fields for level 2 are:

- a) All relation links to metadata (`describedby`) and content resources (`item`)

^{xiii} assessed at <https://www.f-ujl.net/index.php?action=test>. Assessment date: 12.12.2024

^{xiv} <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/rfc9264/>

- b) Relationships for resource `type` and `collection`, ensuring precise categorization and context
- c) Optional Fields:
 - o Additional fields become mandatory if they offer unique or supplementary information not covered in Level 1, such as multiple metadata formats or alternate representations.

Level 2 extends the minimal implementation of Level 1 by offering richer, resource-specific relationships and a scalable Link Set format. Table 4 compares the differences in implementing core Signposting relation links between Levels 1 and 2.

Aspect	Description	Level 1 Representation	Level 2 Representation
Scope	Defines the range of relation links and their origins	focuses only on links with the landing page as the link origin	Expands this to include content resources and metadata resources from the landing page, offering a complete map of relationships.
Mandatory Fields	Specifies the required relation links	has fewer mandatory links - <code>cite-as</code>	- Landing Page: <code>cite-as</code> , <code>describedby</code> , <code>type</code> , <code>item</code> , <code>license</code> .
		- <code>describedby</code>	- Content Resources: <code>collection</code> , <code>describedby</code> , <code>type</code> (distinct cases).
		- <code>type</code>	- Metadata Resources: <code>describes</code> .
Optional Fields	Additional fields that enhance metadata richness and relationships	- <code>author</code>	Same as Level 1, but fields like <code>author</code> , <code>license</code> , and <code>describedby</code> become mandatory if they provide distinct information.
		- <code>item</code>	
		- <code>license</code>	
		- <code>collection</code>	
Link Cardinality	Specifies the number of links required for each relation type	- <code>cite-as:1</code>	- <code>cite-as:1</code>
		- <code>describedby:1+</code>	- <code>describedby:1+</code>
		- <code>type:1</code>	- <code>type: 2</code> (landing page + object)
			- <code>item:1+</code>
			- <code>describes:1</code>
Link Representation for Discoverability	How the relation links are exposed to machine agents	Links are embedded in HTTP headers and <code><link></code> elements within the HTML <code><head></code>	Consolidates all links into a Linkset document for scalability and machine-readability
Granularity	The level of detail and specificity for content and metadata resources	Focuses only on the scholarly object as a whole.	Handles cases where content or metadata resources differ from the main landing page, providing resource-specific relationships and improving granularity.
Examples	Examples of syntax for implementing the link relations	HTML:	Linkset Document:
		<code><link rel="cite-as" href="https://doi.org/10.1234/example-dataset" /></code>	<code>json{"linkset":[{"rel":"cite-as","href":"https://doi.org/10.1234/example-dataset"}, {"rel":"describedby","href":</code>

		<code><link rel="describedby" href="https://example.com/metadata.json" type="application/json" ></code>	<code>"https://example.com/metadata.json" , "type": "application/json" }, { "rel": "item", "href": "https://example.com/content.pdf", "type": "application/pdf" }] }</code>
		HTTP Header:	
		Link: <code><https://doi.org/10.1234/example-dataset>; rel="cite-as"</code> Link: <code><https://example.com/metadata.json>; rel="describedby"; type="application/json"</code>	

Table 4: Differences of Signposting **Level 1** and **Level 2**

Table 5 highlights the differences in how relation links are implemented in **Level 1** and **Level 2** of FAIR Signposting. Level 1 focuses on providing minimal but essential relation links directly in HTTP headers or HTML. It emphasizes simplicity and accessibility for core metadata and content. Level 2 extends Level 1 by offering a more comprehensive and granular set of relation links, often provided in a standalone Link Set document. This level ensures richer metadata, specific relationships, and support for multiple formats or versions of resources. PIDs are direct links to the digital object and do not differ between levels.

Element	Level 1	Level 2
author	Link to a simple author name or profile page.	Link to an author's ORCID for precise identification.
	Example: https://example.com/article123 → rel="author" → https://example.com/author/JohnDoe	Example: https://example.com/article123 → rel="author" → https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1825-0097
Identifier (cite-as)	Link to a persistent URL for the scholarly object.	Direct citation links to the DOI, often with an explicit identifier path.
	Example: https://example.com/article123 → rel="cite-as" → https://doi.org/10.1234/example.doi	Example: https://example.com/article123 → rel="cite-as" → https://doi.org/10.1234/example.doi/identifier
license	Link to a generic license page.	Link to a specific license URI, such as SPDX identifiers.
	Example: https://example.com/article123 → rel="license" → https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/	Example: https://example.com/article123 → rel="license" → https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-4.0.html
type	Link to a general type, such as an article.	Link to a more specific type of vocabulary for finer granularity.
	Example: https://example.com/article123 → rel="type" → https://schema.org/ScholarlyArticle	Example: https://example.com/article123 → rel="type" → https://purl.org/dc/dcmitype/Text
Content Resources (item)	Link to the object's content or download.	Link to different formats or versions of content.
	Example: https://example.com/article123 → rel="item" → https://example.com/content/article123.pdf	Example: https://example.com/article123 → rel="item" → https://example.com/content/article123.xml
Metadata Resources (describedby)	Link to a basic metadata description.	Link to richer metadata standards or schemas.
	Example: https://example.com/article123 → rel="describedby" → https://example.com/metadata/basic.xml	Example: https://example.com/article123 → rel="describedby" → https://example.com/metadata/full.rdf

Table 5: FAIR Signposting relation links at HTTP Header and HTML representations examples.

While Level 1 provides essential relation links to enable basic discovery and navigation, Level 2 extends Level 1 by offering comprehensive and granular relation links for richer metadata and multiple versions/formats of resources to guide assessment tools to improve FAIR scores.

4 Assessment methods and tools

FAIR assessments based on automatic tools [28], [29], [30], online self-assessment surveys [31], [32], [33], [34], manual [35], [36], [37] and hybrid methods [38] exist. The metric framework designed to enable automated assessments, often used within these tools, is the FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics [39]. It introduces 17 assessment metrics aligned with FAIR principles and incorporates community standards, such as the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model [36] and CoreTrustSeal^{xv} requirements. This framework is widely adopted for its potential to provide standardized, machine-actionable metrics for improving FAIRness assessments.

Recent research has provided a comprehensive analysis of tools and checklists designed to evaluate the FAIRness of datasets. The authors compare the features and requirements, methodologies, and results of tools/checklists [40], [41], [42], [38]. These papers also assess datasets across different repositories using these tools [43], uncovering disparities in FAIRness evaluation. Discrepancies in the subjective interpretation of FAIR principles across tools lead to inconsistencies in FAIR scores since these scores vary significantly, indicating a lack of standardization. The overall conclusion among these papers is that scores across tools are very significant due to differences in implementation and interpretation of FAIR principles and user accessibility [44]; non-expert users face difficulties due to complex interfaces and inconsistent terminologies. These papers underscored the need for standardized FAIRness evaluation methodologies to ensure consistent and reliable assessments [45]. These findings highlight the importance of specific guidelines and FAIR principles harmonization practices, which influence FAIRness evaluations.

^{xv} <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>

5. FAIR Signposting Implementing Stories: challenges, guidance, and achievements

The implementation approach for FAIR Signposting began with the use of HTTP headers or HTML at Level 1, enabling the exposure of machine-readable links to Persistent Identifiers (PIDs), metadata, and content. This step ensures basic machine actionability and aligns with FAIR. The focus remained on identifying central landing pages as key points for exposing these links effectively, ensuring datasets became increasingly machine-readable and accessible to automated assessment tools.

5.1 FAIR Signposting implementation at GESIS

GESIS – the Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences^{xvi} provides essential and internationally relevant research-based services for the social sciences. Among those services are survey studies on crucial social issues investigating human behavior over the decades, consequently generating vast amounts of data in various formats from questionnaires. GESIS data is stored and made available through the GESIS Search^{xvii}, a data platform containing information about social science research data and open-access publications. Following a user-centered design approach, the study descriptions are linked with the associated datasets, which are also available for download. The GESIS data archive offers more than 6,500 national and international studies for secondary analysis that can be ordered user-friendly. Users can find research data as variables from questionnaires from relevant social science surveys data, such as the General Population Survey of the Social Sciences (ALLBUS), General Population Survey of the Social Sciences (ISSP), Eurobarometer, Politbarometer, German Longitudinal Election Study (GLES), European Values Study (EVS), GESIS Panel (GPANEL), Programme for the International Assessment of Adult Competencies (PIAAC), among others.

For this project, we have implemented the FAIR Signposting level 1 profile at GESIS and all use case partners' examples. We assessed the FAIRness of datasets in repositories using the F-UJI FAIR data assessment tool [8]. Before and after the implementation of the FAIR Signposting representation. The assessment results are depicted in Figure 4. At GESIS, the Project's team tested Signposting, and an example can be found at DOI 10.4232/1.11372 (<https://doi.org/10.4232/1.11372>, landing page [GESIS-Suche: International Social Survey Programme: Citizenship - ISSP 2004](#)):

- a) Signposting relation links were provided in the HTML head element, like in the example:

```
<!-- FAIR Signposting typed links -->  
  <link rel="type" href="https://schema.org/Dataset">  
  <link rel="type" href="https://schema.org/AboutPage">  
  <link rel="describedby" type="application/ld+json"  
href="/getSchemaOrg.php?id=ZA3950">
```

- b) Signposting relation links can also be provided in the header of the HTTP response. The GESIS example would look like the following if provided in the header.

^{xvi} <https://www.gesis.org/home>

^{xvii} <https://search.gesis.org>

Link: <https://schema.org/Dataset>; rel="type",

<https://schema.org/AboutPage> ; rel="type",

<https://search.gesis.org/getSchemaOrg.php?id=ZA3950>; rel="describedby";
type="application/ld+json"

Use the "describedby" link to provide metadata for distribution/license/access conditions/PROV-O. Below are the metadata from the GESIS example (here, JSON-LD is used by the Project's team)

c) distribution of the data set, including encoding/url/size

```
"distribution": [  
  {  
    "@type": "DataDownload",  
    "name": "ZA3950_v1-3-0.sav (Dataset) 17.07 MB",  
    "encodingFormat": "application/x-spss-sav",  
    "contentUrl": "https://access.gesis.org/dbk/46695",  
    "contentSize": "17898386"  
  },  
  {  
    "@type": "DataDownload",  
    "name": "ZA3950_v1-3-0.dta (Dataset) 15.07 MB",  
    "encodingFormat": "application/x-stata-dta",  
    "contentUrl": "https://access.gesis.org/dbk/46693",  
    "contentSize": "15798560"  
  },  
  {  
    "@type": "DataDownload",  
    "name": "ZA3950_v1-3-0.por (Dataset) 28.26 MB",  
    "encodingFormat": "application/x-spss-por",  
    "contentUrl": "https://access.gesis.org/dbk/46694",  
    "contentSize": "29634390"  
  }  
]
```

d) license information

```
"license":  
"https://www.gesis.org/fileadmin/upload/dienstleistung/daten/umfragedaten/_bgordnung_bestellen/2023-06-30_Usage_regulations.pdf",
```

e) access conditions information

```
"conditionsOfAccess": "This dataset can be accessed for logged-in accounts  
at https://search.gesis.org/ZA3950",  
"isAccessibleForFree": "true",
```

f) Provenance info in PROV-O

```
"prov:wasRevisionOf": [
  {
    "@id": "https://doi.org/10.4232/1.10078"
  }
]
```

The FAIRness scores of the test DOI at GESIS have now shown measurable improvement with implementing FAIR Signposting, addressing several challenges highlighted in the earlier analysis. Previously, as noted in the European landscape study [7], assessing GESIS's FAIRness using tools like F-UJI revealed systematic weaknesses. These included unavoidable licensing restrictions and technical issues where metadata, although present, was not represented in a machine-readable format harmonized across different assessment tools [8]. With FAIR Signposting, assessment tools can evaluate and provide a fair score, reflecting the metadata available, which is now also readable. This standardization addresses the earlier technical limitations, allowing tools like F-UJI to recognize and evaluate the metadata more effectively.

With the integration of FAIR Signposting, GESIS has enhanced its ability to provide machine-readable links and metadata, improving findability and overall FAIR compliance. Figure 4 shows GESIS dataset's improvement before (43%) and after (79%) scores by implementing FAIR Signposting representation. An increase of 36% was achieved.

Figure 4: Before and after assessment results for FAIR Signposting at GESIS. DOI: 10.4232/1.11372^{xviii}.

^{xviii} assessed at <https://www.f-ujl.net/index.php?action=test>. Assessment date: 12.12.2024

5.2 FAIR Signposting implementation at use case partners

We started with a selection of datasets for evaluation of FAIR scores of Datasets from use case partners, and the following datasets have been identified for primary checks:

- lifbi.de
 - <http://dx.doi.org/10.5157/NEPS:SC1:10.1.0>
- dipf.de
 - <https://doi.org/10.7477/4:1:0>
 - <https://doi.org/10.18442/118>
- diw.de
 - <https://portal.fdz-bo.diw.de/study/S0017>
 - <https://www.diw.de/sixcms/detail.php?id=838674>
- dzwh.eu
 - <https://metadata.fdz.dzwh.eu/de/data-packages/stu-sid2021?page=1&size=10&type=surveys&version=1.0.0>
 - <https://doi.org/10.21249/DZHW:wegequaliteachers:1.0.0>

We assessed the FAIRness Scores of these datasets for comparison purposes. We advised all use case partners how to check the FAIR Signposting relation links, which are often invisible to humans as defined in the HTTP headers or the HTML head element of landing pages. To make these relation links visible, we advised non-technicians to use tools such as Signposting Sniffing (a Chrome browser extension^{xix}), or Signposting Validation/Check Service, running as an FDO Service in the FDO Demo environment. This service, developed at GESIS, provides a simple and efficient way to validate and check the implementation of Signposting on DOIs and landing pages. It is designed to help partners ensure that their Signposting is implemented correctly^{xx}.

HTML source. For example, on the GESIS landing page https://search.gesis.org/research_data/ZA5252, the following snippet can be found in the header:

```
<link rel="type" href="https://schema.org/Dataset">  
<link rel="type" href="https://schema.org/AboutPage">  
<link rel="describedby" type="application/ld+json" href="/getSchemaOrg.php?id=ZA5252">
```

For technical staff, we advised using the **curl command** or browser **developer tools** to inspect the HTML source:

- Use the curl command with -i option to display the HTML with headers
- Use the development tool in the browser to see the HTML with the headers

During the project, we:

^{xix} https://chromewebstore.google.com/detail/signposting-sniffing/pahanegeimljfcnjoglnamnlcgipmbc?hl=en-US&utm_source=ext_sidebar

^{xx} PID Registration Service. (See section 6.2)

- Provided guidance to use case partners to implement signposting solutions
- Conducted before and after evaluations of research objects' FAIRness were performed
- Metadata was linked with the Signposting specifications
- In all cases, linked metadata of research objects received a higher FAIRness score through FAIR Signposting [46]

The Signposting Implementation Story for each use case partner is explained in detail through sections 5.2.1 to 5.2.4.

5.2.1 LIfBi: Signposting Implementing Story

The Leibniz Institute for Educational Trajectories (LIfBi)^{xxi} in Bamberg investigates educational processes from birth to old adulthood. To promote longitudinal research in educational science in Germany, the LIfBi provides a fundamental, nationally and internationally significant, research-based infrastructure for empirical educational research. The institute's core is the National Educational Panel Study (NEPS), which is based at the LIfBi and combines the expertise of a Germany-wide, interdisciplinary network of excellence.

a) Challenges:

An initial review of data led to the discovery of inconsistencies and gaps in metadata implementation, with LIfBi questioning why specific datasets were not adequately represented in assessments of FAIR compliance. LIfBi faced technical limitations due to their Content Management System (CMS) (DNN) and the unavailability of administrative rights to modify the core configuration files.

- Technical limitations:
 - Lack of administrative rights and restrictions within the CMS hindered the immediate implementation of recommended changes
 - Structural issues in metadata repositories, such as missing OAI-PMH endpoints, further complicate compliance with FAIR principles
- Complexity of standards:
 - Navigating FAIR guidelines, especially nuanced elements like the "profile" attribute in JSON-LD, demanded a high level of technical understanding.
 - Ambiguities in external system configurations, such as the "gesis.neps" mapping, further increased the implementation complexity. This additional source of complexity emerged during the F-UJI evaluation due to the client ID "gesis.neps" in the metadata retrieved from DataCite.
 - Historically, DOIs were registered via *dalra*, creating cross-references within the DataCite infrastructure and storing related metadata. As part of this process, *dalra* assigned the client ID "gesis.neps" to indicate the origin of the reference. However, the implementation team was unaware of this identifier, making it difficult to trace its provenance or interpret its significance during automated FAIR assessments.
- Resource constraints:

^{xxi} www.lifbi.de

- Because LfBi's web admins were managing multiple priorities, the resolution of technical issues was delayed
- The iterative nature of testing and feedback required sustained effort over an extended period

b) Guidance:

The Project's team provided detailed guidance, including methods to edit headers via CMS settings and a workaround using individual page-level settings for adding FAIR signposting relation links. LfBi explored these methods but faced limitations, such as restricted file upload formats (e.g., .json files requiring renaming) and technical hurdles related to dynamic versus static content.

- Iteration and testing:
 - LfBi made multiple attempts to implement FAIR metadata using the provided guidance. Testing with tools like F-UJI revealed further obstacles, including compatibility issues with file extensions and incomplete metadata.
 - The collaboration extended to refining JSON-LD formats, understanding the "profile" attribute, and addressing discrepancies in metadata harvesting from external repositories.
- Breakthroughs and adjustments:
 - The realization that metadata records lacked OAI-PMH endpoints provided a critical insight. This deficiency was directly linked to missing scores for specific FAIR criteria.
 - LfBi acknowledged challenges in their repository setup and explored potential solutions. Adding the OAI-PMH endpoint will further improve the score.

c) Achievements:

- FAIRness score improvements:
 - LfBi's efforts, supported by guidance from the Project's team, led to a significant improvement in their F-UJI score, from 41% to 83%, as depicted in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Before and after assessment results for FAIR Signposting at LfBi. DOI: 10.5157/NEPS:SC1:10.1.0.

- Improved FAIR Compliance:
 - LfBi increased its F-UJI score to 83%, reflecting substantial progress in metadata quality and discoverability
- Knowledge building:
 - LfBi gained a better understanding of FAIR principles, metadata standards, and repository configurations
- Next steps for future improvements:
 - The identification of structural gaps, such as missing OAI-PMH endpoints, sets the stage for future projects aimed at achieving full FAIR compliance
- Strengthened collaboration:
 - The exchange of expertise and iterative problem-solving fostered a productive relationship between LfBi and the Project’s team

Table 6 summarizes the guidance and suggestions for improving current challenges:

Aspect	Current Challenge	Suggested Improvement
Utilization of CMS Options	Page-level header changes are not scalable.	Combine global “web.config” changes with page-level SEO settings for a balanced solution.
Expanding Metadata	F-UJI score did not improve due to limited additional metadata fields.	Add fields like “license”, “distribution”, “conditionsOfAccess”, “isAccessibleForFree”, and “prov:wasRevisionOf” in a JSON-LD file linked via ‘describedby’.
File Format Issues	“.json” files cannot be uploaded due to restrictions, requiring “.json.txt”.	Enable “.json” uploads through webmasters or use an external repository with the correct MIME settings for the JSON file.
Metadata Discoverability	Missing OAI-PMH endpoints in re3data records caused F-UJI warnings.	Add OAI-PMH endpoints to re3data records in collaboration with repository maintainers.
Metadata Types and Links	Dataset links, file sizes, and access conditions were not fully included.	Add comprehensive metadata with detailed dataset links, file sizes, and access conditions.
Testing and Validation	Gaps in metadata interpretation by F-UJI during testing.	Use multiple validation tools (e.g., F-UJI, FAIR Data Validator) to cross-check metadata compliance before implementation.
Long-Term Strategy	Lack of dynamic header support in the current CMS and incomplete metadata.	Consider transitioning to a CMS that supports dynamic content or integrating plugins/extensions for advanced metadata management.

Table 6: Strategies for Enhancing FAIR Compliance and Metadata Management in LfBi’s DNN-Based System

5.2.2 DIPF: Signposting Implementing Story

Leibniz Institute for Research and Information in Education (DIPF)^{xxii} The DIPF addresses educational challenges through empirical research, digital infrastructure, and knowledge transfer. Supporting scientists, policymakers, and practitioners, it uniquely integrates research, transfer, and infrastructure in Germany. The institute focuses on key areas such as early childhood education, instructional quality, support for at-risk children, and the effects of educational reforms. DIPF provides innovative digital services, including reference systems, data collections, and transfer tools, while producing educational reports, analyses, and evaluations to improve the quality of education. Its interdisciplinary, networked approach combines theoretical, empirical, and historical insights to study systemic, institutional, and individual educational processes.

a) Challenges:

- Initial F-UJI Score and metadata accessibility:
 - The DIPF dataset landing page received a F-UJI score 50, indicating moderate FAIR compliance but significant room for improvement.
- Metadata accessibility by F-UJI:
 - Metadata was generated through PHP scripts, but it was not consistently visible to tools like F-UJI, limiting the discoverability and interoperability of the data.
 - The schema.org metadata is already being generated using PHP, but it is not consistently accessible to F-UJI. This is likely due to how the metadata is embedded or exposed in the system.
 - The lack of specific metadata fields, such as `prov:wasRevisionOf`, remains limited due to unavailable data in the current database structure.
- Handcrafted system:
 - DIPF's system for displaying datasets was custom-built and lacked a standardized CMS, which complicated the integration of FAIR signposting.
 - The unstructured nature of the information system made identifying optimal points for inserting metadata harder.

b) Guidance

- Technical recommendations:
 - Utilize Existing PHP Scripts:
The project's team recommended building upon DIPF's existing PHP scripts to generate FAIR signposting relation links (e.g., `cite-as`, `describedby`) and embed them in HTTP headers.
 - Schema.org Metadata Integration:
Enhance the current PHP-generated schema.org metadata by ensuring visibility to external tools and aligning it with FAIR principles.
 - The suggestion to use existing PHP scripts to enhance metadata and add FAIR signposting is included.
 - Review the current PHP implementation for schema.org metadata
 - Adapt the script to include HTTP header modifications

^{xxii} <https://www.dipf.de/de>

- Test the updated script in the staging environment to validate F-UJI compliance.
- Stepwise approach:
 - Focus on incremental improvements to achieve quick wins, such as implementing Signposting Level 1 via HTTP headers for essential FAIR compliance.
- Collaboration and support:
 - The project's team offered examples and technical templates tailored to DIPF's requirements, facilitating smoother implementation.

c) Achievements

- Progress on implementation:
 - DIPF began implementing FAIR signposting in their staging environment, with partial metadata fields mapped to schema.org and HTTP headers.
- Enhancements to metadata:
 - The inclusion of the `prov:generatedAtTime` element to capture the timestamp when the dataset was created. This aligns with the W3C PROV ontology specification and addresses gaps in temporal metadata, enhancing FAIRness evaluations.
 - The addition of the `@context` element in JSON-LD metadata to reference namespaces such as schema.org and prov, improving machine interpretability and interoperability.
- Score improvement:
 - The DIPF landing page for datasets increased their **F-UJI score from 50 to 83**, indicating a slight improvement, as demonstrated in Figure 6:

Figure 6: Before and after assessment results for FAIR Signposting at DIPF. DOI: 10.7477/6:1:24

- Increased awareness and collaboration:
 - DIPF's team, including developers, better understood FAIR principles and the technical requirements for compliance.
- Next steps for improvements:
 - With the groundwork laid in the staging environment, DIPF is well-positioned to significantly increase its F-UJI score once the implementation is completed.

5.2.3 DIW/SOEP: Signposting Implementing Story

The German Socio-Economic Panel (SOEP) is based at the German Institute for Economic Research (DIW)^{xxiii}. The SOEP-Core^{xxiv} is the central piece of the Socio-Economic Panel and yearly surveys of the living situation and attitudes of more than 15,000 households and about 30,000 people since 1984. The study „*Leben in Deutschland*“ (“Living in Germany”) is the most extensive longitudinal (long-term) study of social developments in Germany, being enlarged in 1990 due to the German reunification to encompass a sample from East Germany. The datasets provide information on all household members: Germans living in the former eastern and western German states, foreign citizens, and immigrants residing in Germany. Since 2016, the study has been widened with a sample of refugees. Some topics include household composition, occupational biographies, employment, earnings, health, and satisfaction indicators.

The DIW office in Berlin registers the SOEP-Core complexity information through extensive documentation on Topics of SOEP-Core, survey design, data editions and distribution files, and orientation on how to use the SOEP-Core data through the SOEPcompanion^{xxv} website. The portal paneldata.org provides the details on 671 survey instruments (with 38161 questions) and 570 datasets (with 114414 variables)^{xxvi} interface, where variable landing pages are available.

a) Challenges:

- Initial F-UJI Score:
 - The DIW dataset landing page received a F-UJI score 50, indicating moderate FAIR compliance. Key issues included incomplete metadata and a lack of adherence to required schema.org attributes.
- CMS limitation:
 - SixCMS, the CMS in use, is a proprietary system with limited publicly available documentation, making it challenging to modify HTTP headers or implement FAIR signposting. The initial score was achieved because the CMS provided some relevant information by default.

b) Guidance

Technical recommendations:

- Realize the introduction of additional information, including a link to a JSON-LD file, into the HTML header of the landing page:
 - `<link rel="type" href="https://schema.org/Dataset">`
`<link rel="type" href="https://schema.org/AboutPage">`
`<link rel="describedby" type="application/ld+json"`
`href="https://www.diw.de/tmp/10.5684_soep.core.v38.1eu.json">`.

^{xxiii} <https://www.diw.de>

^{xxiv} Latest version: <http://doi.org/10.5684/soep.core.v39o>.

^{xxv} <https://companion.soep.de> |

^{xxvi} <https://paneldata.org/soep-core>

- Introduce standardized information on the license within the JSON file:
 - {
 - "@context": [
 - "https://schema.org/",
 - {
 - "prov": <http://www.w3.org/ns/prov#>
 -],
 - "license": https://www.diw.de/en/diw_01.c.601584.en/data_access.html
- Stepwise implementation approach:
 - Test incremental updates in a controlled environment (e.g., one DOI landing page) before scaling to other datasets.
 - Use the provided Google Docs example and the Project's team JSON-LD examples as templates.
- Collaboration and support:
 - Organized meetings with DIW's technical team to facilitate direct communication and troubleshooting.
 - Provided ongoing email support with detailed responses to technical questions, including tailored examples.

c) Achievements

Figure 7 shows how DIW successfully improved the F-UJI score from 50 to 54% by addressing metadata deficiencies, including adding a valid license attribute.

Figure 7: Before and after assessment results for FAIR Signposting at DIW. DOI: 10.5684/soep.core.v38.1eu

- Enhanced metadata quality:
 - The introduction of a link to a JSON-LD file opened a way to provide standardized metadata information about the digital object the landing page is about.
- Increased understanding of FAIR Standards:
 - DIW's technical team understood how to implement FAIR signposting and align metadata with schema.org requirements.
- Established framework for further updates:

- The Project team provided examples and templates that enabled DIW to continue improving metadata quality systematically. There is the option for DIW to use the insights and provide more information in the JSON file while migrating the DOI registration to DataCite Fabrica.

With further updates to metadata, including attributes like distribution and identifier, DIW's F-UJI score could rise to 65–75%. Comprehensive updates across all dataset landing pages could push compliance closer to 85–90%.

d) Suggestions received from DIW use case partner:

- Better Documentation: The need for a mapping document to link schema.org attributes to F-UJI metrics: a comprehensive mapping document linking schema.org attributes to F-UJI metrics, as this would reduce the trial-and-error process and make implementation more efficient.
- Mapping documentation: proposed creating a three-column mapping document:
 - F-UJI metrics
 - Corresponding schema.org attributes
 - Example JSON-LD representations
- Incorporating DDI-Codebook metadata:
 - DIW can generate DDI-Codebook metadata for the digital object, providing significantly more detailed information in a 470MB XML file. A standardized option should specify a qualified link to this metadata, indicating: 'Here is an XML file in the standard DDI-Codebook 2.5 format, which describes the digital object.'
- Most of the metadata required for DOI registration of a digital object can be provided by the registration organization (currently da-ra, and in the future, DataCite). They could supply this information in a JSON-LD file and host it, allowing DIW to provide a link to the JSON-LD file simply.

5.2.4 DZHW: Signposting Implementing Story

The German Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies (DZHW)^{xxvii} conducts application-oriented empirical research on higher education and science systems. With its data and analyses, the DZHW supports politics, universities, and educational administration in developing higher education in Germany and Europe.

a) Challenges

- Low FAIR Score:
 - The DZHW landing page for data packages received an initial F-UJI score of 47, reflecting limited compliance with FAIR principles.
 - The primary issue was using client-side JavaScript to generate schema.org metadata, which F-UJI and similar tools could not detect.
- Metadata accessibility:
 - Although schema.org metadata was embedded in the HTML, it was not generated server-side or made available through HTTP headers, a key requirement for FAIR compliance.
- Handcrafted Information System:
 - The system used for DZHW's landing pages appeared custom-built, lacking streamlined processes for integrating FAIR signposting, such as using server-side scripts.
- Resource constraints:
 - DZHW relied on an external IT service provider, whose limited availability caused significant delays in addressing technical issues.

b) Guidance

- Technical recommendations:
 - Suggested generating schema.org JSON metadata server-side to make it accessible via a static HTTP URL.
 - Recommended using server-side scripts (e.g., PHP) to add FAIR signposting relation links to the HTTP headers of the landing pages.
- Leverage the Existing Project's team Scripts:
 - The project's team offered to adapt their previously developed PHP script for DZHW's use.
- Offer of support:
 - The project's team offered to provide a script for generating FAIR signposting metadata, contingent on collaboration with DZHW's technical team or service provider.
 - Focus on implementing Signposting Level 1 via static HTTP headers as a quick win requiring minimal architectural changes.
- Supportive collaboration:
 - The project's team provided proactive follow-ups and reminders, offering conceptual guidance and technical solutions.

^{xxvii} Cf. https://www.dzhw.eu/gmbh/index_html.

c) **Achievements**

- Enhanced awareness:
 - DZHW gained a clearer understanding of its metadata shortcomings and the steps required to achieve FAIR compliance.
 - Consensus on Next Steps:
DZHW and the Project's team agreed on the need for server-side metadata generation and the inclusion of FAIR signposting in HTTP headers.
- Preparation for implementation:
 - By proposing a conceptual meeting, DZHW signalled its intent to move forward once technical resources became available.
- Next steps for improvement:
 - The identified steps, once implemented, are expected to significantly improve the F-UJI score, potentially raising it from 47 to 80+, depending on the comprehensiveness of the updates.

6 FAIR Signposting Best Practices

FAIR Signposting is open-data oriented, and in the context of Open Science, it serves as a foundational mechanism to enhance the discoverability, accessibility, and usability of data by establishing explicit relationships between data, metadata, and persistent identifiers (PIDs). These complex relationships in the diagram highlight the interconnectedness of FAIR data, metadata, PIDs, assessment tools, and stakeholders:

- FAIRness is evaluated using tools that rely on global standards and schemas
- Metadata and PIDs are key for findability and interoperability
- Stakeholders utilize FAIR scores to inform data reuse and compliance decisions
- Harmonized approaches ensure consistency in applying FAIR principles across tools and repositories

Figure 8: Interconnectedness of the FAIR data ecosystem and the FAIR Signposting.

Understanding these relationships is crucial to evaluating and adopting the best practices for FAIR Signposting. Data association with metadata ("hasMetadata") ensures that descriptive information is readily available, making the data interpretable and machine-readable. PIDs ("hasPID") provide globally resolvable identifiers that guarantee unique identification and long-term accessibility of datasets.

These PIDs are further linked to metadata ("isAssociatedWith"), creating a cohesive framework for improving findability and enabling precise connections between data and its descriptive elements. FAIR data principles are evaluated by assessment tools ("isMeasuredBy") that rely on standards and terminologies ("ComplyWith") to ensure interoperability and consistency across domains. These evaluations are critical for stakeholders ("MakeDecision"), such as research funders, repositories, and policymakers, who use FAIR scores to inform funding, compliance, and

reuse decisions. FAIR assessment tools play a crucial role for researchers, funders, and data repositories by promoting transparency and accountability in data management. FAIR Signposting itself ("IsKeyforFindability") leverages standardized link relations (e.g., `describedby`, `cite-as`) to automate the discovery and accessibility of datasets, harmonizing interpretation and implementation of FAIR principles across tools and communities ("Harmonized Interpretation"). This interconnected system positions FAIR Signposting as a vital enabler of Open Science, supporting transparent, reusable, and interoperable research outputs.

6.1 Best Practices for Implementing and Validating FAIR Signposting

- a) **Start small:**
 - Begin with Signposting Level 1 using basic HTTP headers, focusing on key link relations like `cite-as`, `describedby`, and `item`
- b) **Adopt Persistent Identifiers (PIDs):**
 - Ensure all entities (datasets, authors, institutions) have globally unique and resolvable PIDs
- c) **Use `linksets` for scalability:**
 - Move to Level 2 with `linkset` documents for complex metadata structures and relationships
- d) **Align metadata with standards:**
 - Map legacy metadata to standards like DataCite or Schema.org
- e) **Promote community engagement:**
 - Share implementation experiences through workshops, conferences, and institutional networks
- f) **Validate and iterate:**
 - Use validation tools and community feedback to refine implementations. If tools are unreliable, focus on peer-reviewed validation
- g) **Diagram relationships:**
 - Visually map signposting nodes and connections to clarify implementation strategies

6.2 FAIR Signposting validators

Tools for Validating Signposting Implementation are available. We recommend using these tools to check and validate that the FAIR Signposting relation links are present and correct. These are the tools for partners implementing Signposting on their DOIs and landing pages. By using these tools, they can:

- Validate the presence and correctness of Signposting relation links
- Ensure compliance with FAIR principles
- Improve metadata discoverability and machine-actionability

Some options are:

a) Using a browser extension

- Example: Signposting Sniffing, an extension on Chrome^{xxviii}

b) Using a Signposting Validator / such as the Signposting Check FDO Service in the Gesis FDO Demo.

- Access via API: access the service programmatically using an API request.
 - For example:
https://<anonymous_server>/doip/api/fdoservices/invoke/FDS_SIGNPOSTING_CHECK?pid=10.4232/1.0068
 - To check multiple DOIs (separated by a comma), such as 10.4232/1.0068 and 10.21249/DZHW:wegequaliteachers:1.0.0, use:
https://<anonymous_server>/doip/api/fdoservices/invoke/FDS_SIGNPOSTING_CHECK?pid=10.4232/1.0068,10.21249/DZHW:wegequaliteachers:1.0.0
- Access via Web Form
 - Go to: https://<anonymous_server>/doip/
 - Go to **"Invoke an FDO Service on FDOs"**
 - Select the **"SIGNPOSTING CHECK"** service from the dropdown menu an FDO Service
 - Input the DOIs or landing pages, separated by a comma (,)
 - Click **"Invoke"** to run the validation
 - Example request for two DOIs (10.4232/1.0068 and 10.21249/DZHW:wegequaliteachers:1.0.0) would look like this:
https://<anonymous_server>doip/fdoservices/invoke?id=FDS_SIGNPOSTING_CHECK&pid=10.4232/1.0068,10.21249/DZHW:wegequaliteachers:1.0.0

Figure 9 depicts the interface example of Signposting Validation/Check Service, running as an FDO Service:

*** NEW *** Invoke an FDO Service on FDOs

Select an FDO Service: FDO PIDs (one or more pids separated by a comma, ,):

Type of raw data (Optional, only for get raw data service): CSV (** Temporarily disabled due to security. **) MP3 MPEG

^{xxviii} <https://chromewebstore.google.com/detail/signposting-sniffing/pahanegeimljfcnjoglnamnlcgipmbc>

Invoke FDO Service :
FDS_SIGNPOSTING_CHECK on FDOs :
10.4232/1.0068,10.21249/DZHW:wegequaliteachers:1.0.0

```
{
  "responseCode": 1,
  "type": "Signposting Check",
  "content": [
    {
      "signpostingCheck": {
        "PID": "https://doi.org/10.4232/1.0068",
        "signpostingHtmlLinks": {
          "1": "describedby: \u003chttps://search.gesis.org/getSchema",
          "2": "type: \u003chttps://schema.org/Dataset\u003e",
          "3": "type: \u003chttps://schema.org/AboutPage\u003e"
        },
        "signpostingHttpLinks": {}
      }
    },
    {
      "signpostingCheck": {
        "PID": "https://doi.org/10.21249/DZHW:wegequaliteachers:1.0.0",
        "signpostingHtmlLinks": {},
        "signpostingHttpLinks": {}
      }
    }
  ]
}
```

Figure 9: Signposting Validation/Check Service example

6.3 Best Practices for Validating Signposting

- a) **Automated testing:**
 - Integrate validation into your development pipeline using tools like the FAIR Signposting Validator
- b) **Iterative testing:**
 - Validate implementations during development and after deployment to catch regressions
- c) **Community feedback:**
 - Share results with the Signposting community to ensure adherence to evolving standards

7 Conclusions

The project has significantly improved the findability of data by implementing Signposting specifications, which enhance the accessibility of content and enable machines to discover metadata unambiguously. This approach increases data usability within KonsortSWD-associated data centers, leveraging a low-cost solution to make repositories compliant with FAIR principles. Improving the machine readability of PID metadata also facilitated bots navigating digital objects on the web, further supporting automated processes and efficient data discovery.

7.1 Key recommendations

- Promote FAIR Signposting as a design pattern that supports FAIR principles, ensuring consistency and clarity in FAIR assessments for your resources
- Recommend incorporating Signposting alongside other metadata publications to enhance data discoverability
- Avoid deviations from the Signposting standard to preserve metadata consistency and interpretability
- Support the registration of community standards to increase their visibility and enable validation by FAIR assessment tools
- Use case partners should register as FAIR Signposting adopters at <https://signposting.org/adopters/>, including a list of patterns they have implemented, along with some example URIs

7.2 Future steps

We recommend the following steps. We are looking forward to escalating the method of the FAIR Signposting. A project to improve the findability of datasets on a larger scale is implemented by continuing to expand Signposting specifications as follows:

- Improve Signposting Level 1: Develop scripts that automatically add Signposting relation links in HTML/HTTP headers. It is a feasible approach since some metadata information is standardized (such as DOIs and ORCIDs), and the correct relation link could be assigned accordingly in an automatic manner. By linking these identifiers directly to

datasets via relation links, datasets become more visible and contextually connected to their authors, citations, and descriptions. This directly supports the FAIR principle of findability. Using scripts to automate the embedding of Signposting links improves efficiency, consistency, and scalability since Signposting links (e.g., `author`, `cite-as`, `describedby`) are added systematically and accurately across all datasets or resources. It also significantly reduces the time and effort required to add Signposting links because scripts can handle thousands of datasets or pages simultaneously, making the process scalable and feasible for institutions or projects managing extensive collections.

- Advance to FAIR Signposting Level 2: perform an upgrade at selected use cases (focus on the most relevant studies or datasets) to include `Linkset` documents. `Linkset` documents use standardized formats (e.g., RDF or JSON-LD) to express relationships in a machine-readable way, explicating relationships between different resources. By incorporating `Linkset` documents, users are empowered to navigate various resources and discover the dataset and related items, including other datasets, publications, software, metadata records, and more. `Linkset` documents offer a structured approach to expressing relationships between resources, thereby enhancing resource discovery. They provide valuable context that aids users in understanding the significance and applicability of a dataset, facilitate the search for datasets based on their relationships, and simplify the process for researchers to explore interconnected resources. This ultimately aids in finding and reusing data in new studies or reproducing existing research.

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Contact:

Dr Brigitte Mathiak

GESIS – Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences
Knowledge Technologies for the Social Sciences – KTS
Unter Sachsenhausen 6-8, D-50667 Cologne
www.gesis.org
brigitte.mathiak@gesis.org
Tel.: +49 (0)221 - 47694 - 510

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